

Digital Transformation in Social Work Training and Service Delivery in Nigeria: A Systematic Literature Review

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18520193>

Abstract

Digital technology has revolutionized social work training and service delivery with its ability to bring about innovation in practice systems. Gone are the days when a social worker can only deliver his service face-to-face or receive training in the four walls of the classroom. Now the social worker can connect, share knowledge and experience and support one another or their clients across borders. This shift has made training and service delivery for social workers easier, better and faster. It has also widened access to quality programmes and enhance personalised learning experience. However, the transformation of these field of study is not without issues. Challenges may come in form of data breaches, maintaining privacy and confidentiality of clients, ethical issues. To navigate this digital landscape, social workers must take deliberate steps to ensure a bright future and this will require careful planning and strategic implementation. This will require identifying the knowledge gaps/training needs of social workers in the digital environment as well as providing social workers with adequate information needed to navigate the changes technology brings. This study leveraged existing knowledge to develop sustainable approaches to digital technology use. This paper having synthesise empirical findings from literature on how digital technologies are integrated into social work practices and recommended based on the knowledge gaps identified, that social workers should be exposed to information literacy/digital marketing, they must be given the needed support to make learning easy and desirable and they should use digital platforms constantly to enhance their digital competencies. This will enable them to accept and use technology in the right way and right manner for sustainability while ensuring safety.

Keywords: Digital technology, social work, training, Service delivery, Digital transformation, information literacy, Digital marketing.

Introduction

In recent times, technology has pervaded all areas of human life including their lifestyle and workplace. The invention of digital technologies also known as information and communication technology has made all aspect of work life easy. It has altered all fields including social work leading to changes in values and ethics. In the Olden days for instance before a social worker can

deliver his/her services to the clientele, he/she will have to meet the client physically in a mutually agreed location but reverse is the case nowadays as the social worker does not necessarily have to meet the client. They can now conduct their sessions online with the use of instrument of technology. Digital age has transformed how social workers connect, share knowledge, experience and support each other especially through peer learning networks like social media groups and professional forums. Digital transformation came into being with the emergence of the internet and other digital tools. Digital skills and knowledge are hallmarks of 21st century generation. Digitalization in social work refers to the use of digital tools, technologies, and platforms to support, enhance, and sometimes transform traditional social work practices (Mishna, Milne, Bogo, & Pereira, 2020).

In addition, Barsky, (2021) stated that these tools range from communication technologies, such as teleconferencing and instant messaging, to more sophisticated systems like artificial intelligence (AI) for case management or predictive analytics for risk assessments. Social workers can also leverage data analytics to better understand client needs, predict outcomes, and tailor interventions accordingly (Barsky, 2021). Digital technologies have changed the way we interact with others, giving rise to new areas of specialisation, such as online interventions or diagnoses based on the analysis of user behaviour in social networks, remote patient monitoring, digital health records, AI powered diagnostics and personalised medicine. This enhances collaboration and resource sharing. This has in turn given the social worker a wider outreach and a broader client. Training online for social workers on platforms such as Zoom, YouTube is becoming the popular trend among social workers. Also, nowadays social workers can provide telehealth or teletherapy services to clients on mobile apps. These ranges from apps for online support groups, mental health apps, therapy apps, progress tracker app. For example, telehealth platforms enable social workers to reach clients in rural or underserved areas, overcoming geographical barriers that traditionally limited service delivery (Soska & Johnson, 2020). Digital content delivery, virtual classroom and remote learning with personalized training/adaptive learning systems is now on the rise.

Similarly, digital case management systems can streamline administrative tasks, allowing social workers to spend more time on direct client engagement (Leung & Tsui, 2022). A very useful digital tool for social workers is the Apricot and casebook which allows social workers to organize client information effectively. They can also track progress and generate reports easily. Progress tracker apps can help client track their mental health progress, medication, schedules and therapy need. This makes instant feedback easy. This also makes easy scheduling of appointment and reminders which reduces the risk of missed sessions. The digitalization of social work encompasses both the back-end operations, such as data management and case tracking, and client-facing activities, such as remote counseling or online group therapy sessions (Taylor & McQuaid, 2022).

Online counseling and therapy apps have been shown to increase client engagement, particularly among younger populations who are more comfortable with digital communication (Mishna et al., 2020). In the areas of training for social workers, there seem to be a shift in the way social workers are educated. online training courses like webinars, seminars and workshops has made it easier for social workers to gain access to industry experts from all over the world. Now conferences and seminars can be attended virtually which makes the social worker have access to latest research from industry experts or leaders.

With digital technology, social workers can also pursue continuing education anytime and anywhere and stay current with the latest trends and tools in the field. Social workers can also learn

online and earn certificates and specialisation in areas like digital mental health interventions, teletherapy, telehealth and so on. This will enable the social worker get the needed recognition and advance his career. Furthermore, social workers can now acquire knowledge skills and attitude without much stress using platforms designed for such purposes. In Nigeria, digital transformation of social work training and service delivery comes in the form of the Ondo Abiye mobile health programme, electronic health records, telemedicine and so on. Elechi, Elechi, Onyeugbo, Akujuobi & Nwoda (2024) commented that a noteworthy example is the telehealth program implemented by Precious Gems in Opoji, Edo State which is in collaboration with the World Telehealth Initiative, aimed to improve healthcare access in rural communities.

Rai (2023) cited some examples of digital transformation of social work in several countries which improve efficiency, accessibility and effectiveness and include; Estonia's e-Estonia, which digitizes public services, such as social welfare programs, through an integrated digital platform called X-Road, India's Aadhaar and Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) systems enable efficient and targeted delivery of social welfare benefits, reducing leakages and corruption, South Korea's Smart Work Centers provide digital infrastructure and facilities for remote work thereby addressing regional disparities and promoting work-life balance, Finland's Kela and Digital Services offer a comprehensive suite of digital services, allowing citizens to access online platforms for benefits applications, view payment details, and submit necessary documentation, Singapore's Silver Infocomm Initiative promotes digital inclusion and empowers older adults with digital skills, enabling easy access to social welfare benefits and support services, The United Kingdom's Universal Credit system simplifies the process of receiving multiple welfare benefits by combining multiple benefits into a single payment, Australia's myGov platform provides a centralized portal for accessing various government services, including social welfare programs, Sweden's Försäkringskassan offers e-Services to streamline social welfare processes, allowing citizens to apply for benefits, report changes, and receive notifications online, Canada's Canada Revenue Agency (CRA) and My Account provide secure communication with case officers and personalized information about benefits and entitlements, in the Netherlands, DigiD is a digital identification system used to access various government services, including social welfare programs. These initiatives demonstrate how different countries have embraced digital transformation in their social welfare systems, introducing user friendly platforms, streamlining processes, and providing convenient access to services (Rai, 2023).

Digital tools offer benefits like increased efficiency, personalised learning experience, access to industry experts and mentors, opportunity for collaboration, real time feedback, interactive content, larger outreach opportunity for innovative mental health interventions. However, with digital technology there may be issues of data breaches plus maintaining privacy and confidentiality of clients. This is in line with the statement of Banks (2020) who opened that digital technologies represent both a practical toolset and a conceptual challenge for the profession, inviting a critical re-examination of the core values of social work, including privacy, confidentiality, and equitable service delivery. Digital transformation was accelerated by challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic which necessitated online training and online delivery. Digital transformation will change the profession and skills of social workers and challenge elements of social workers service delivery such as face-to-face interaction.

The digital transformation of the nation has significantly impacted social work and thus necessitating the integration of digital competencies into education and practices. Now it is required that all social workers become technology savvy to be able to effectively practice their

craft. Social workers have been forced to rethink how their professional value or qualities can be applied in new scenarios. Digital transformation goes beyond incorporating technology but includes development of digital skills and competencies. Hence the need for social workers training in digital tools. Even social workers need support to perform their duty. With the Integration of digital technologies in social work, social workers become responsible for the operation of these tools. The social worker digital skills and competencies is essentially for adaptation in this tech savvy world. They should be able to tailor their professional service on digital platforms to specific client needs. The acceptability and use of digital tools are dependent on the desirability of Apps and platforms used for learning and service delivery. This study therefore seeks to answer questions on the benefits, challenges, opportunities and knowledge gaps and how this can be used to enhance social workers use of digital technologies for the transformation of social work training and service delivery

Literature Review

Digital Technologies

Digital technology refers not only to devices such as computers, tablets, and smartphones, but also the multitude of digital activities, including social networking and web browsing, in which people engage today (Omokhabi 2021). While Obar and Wildman (2015) in Omokhabi et al. (2025) describe social media as an internet-based platform that enables communication amongst its users via an online community where they can share ideas, knowledge, and other forms of expression, the concept of digital technology use is extensive that comprises of numerous tools, services, and patterns of usage that are evolving and increasingly transforming people's lives (Omokhabi, 2023). The idea of digital technology use is wide, involving a range of tools, services and usage types that have evolved, and are quickly evolving, altering people's lives (Omokhabi, 2023) These technologies have been widely applied in human activities (Ojokheta & Omokhabi, 2023).

Social Work and Social Workers

The social work has evolved over the last 100 years, and come to mean a practice-based profession that helps people across the human relationship spectrum such as: individuals, families, groups, organisations and communities with social problems to either improve or restore their well-being towards enabling them adjust to their psychosocial functioning as well as to contribute positively to building a functional society in the communities where they belong (Omokhabi,2021) According to Irele (2019), social work is a profession and an academic discipline which supports people to resolve their personal, group and community problems as well as to restore or enhance their capacity for social functioning. Different scholars and schools of social work have attempted to define social work, but have hinged their perspectives on the broad definitions of professional bodies such as the National Association of Social Work (NASW) and the International Federation of Social Workers (IFSW)(Omokhabi,2021). Respect for diversity, human rights, social justice, and collective responsibility are the cornerstones of social work (Omokhabi, Omokhabi, & Omilani ,2025). Social work is a social institution because it is a social intervention which encourages, enriches and increases the capabilities of individuals, families and groups to socially function in their communities (Udeani, 2019 in Omokhabi & Fajimi ,2021)

Social workers are dedicated professionals who strive to enhance the welfare of both individuals and communities by addressing their diverse and fundamental needs (Andermann, 2016;). The practice of social work involves understanding human development, behaviour, social, economic and cultural institutions and interactions (Sharma & Gupta, 2022). This field involves working with diverse individuals and groups, with a special focus on supporting

those who are vulnerable, oppressed or living in poverty (Davis & Reber, 2016), as well as participation in governmental and statutory processes that lead to the creation of government or social programmes. Social workers play a critical role in tackling social inequalities and obstacles that stand in the way of their clients' well-being, and are saddled with responsibilities include issues such as poverty, unemployment, prejudice, and inadequate housing (Mupedziswa, 2020 cited in Omokhabi & Omokhabi,2023)

Digital Social Work

Digitisation introduces innovations that change behaviour and work. Social workers have traditionally done their work through writing letters or making telephone calls in their offices. The adaptation of innovations brings new methodologies into social work practice. This has resulted in the emergence of digital social work otherwise known as e-social work as a new specialty. Social work is absorbing digital-based intervention strategies, and this is refining the nature of practice (Del Fresno Garca, 2015) as social workers gain awareness and develop competences for modern social work practice with the use of digital technologies (Kirwan,2019 in Omokhabi,2022). Social workers utilise e-social work to complement face-to-face interface in educational and client-services. They use social media tools like Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Twitter and LinkedIn as well as media sharing sites like Flickr, Vimeo and YouTube. They also use content creation and publishing tools like Wikis and Blogs and internet chat services like Google, Hangout, Skype, Whatsapp messenger and Facebook messenger (Omokhabi, 2022). Literature shows that digital tools are being used in social work education for training and practice for diagnosis, intervention and evaluation (Goldkind Wolf & Freddolino, 2018).

Methodology

This paper through critical analysis of empirical findings and analysis of data from secondary sources such as official publications, literature, textbooks, journals, and conference papers aims to provide insight on digital transformation of social work training and service delivery in Nigeria. This study reviewed both international and local findings to draw conclusion. These sources were obtained manually through searching of the internet for keywords obtained from the title. The keywords include digital transformation social work, e-social work, technology in social work training, Digital service delivery, Nigeria. This review included recent studies (English) on the discourse published from 2020 till date and studies older than that was excluded. The search yielded a lot of publications from which the researcher purposively selected the relevant ones. SWOT Analysis was used to draw out implications for digital adoption in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

The theory adopted for this study is the technology Acceptance Model by Fred Davis.

Technology Acceptance Model

Davis (1986) developed one of the most commonly utilized models for estimating an individual's application and acceptance of information technology, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). According to Davis (1986), a user's intention to utilize a technology will largely determine how they use it in the end. The user's intention is influenced by his attitude towards using a technology. To him, the attitude is determined by the perceived usefulness of the technology and the perceived ease of use which are hypothesized to be the fundamental determinants of user acceptance. Jesa (2023) stated that in the original TAM, Davis (1986, 1989) included the following dimensions: perceived utility (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU), attitude, and behavioral intention to use. In addition, that PU and PEOU, among the constructs, form how users think of technology and predict their attitude regarding it, which implies its adoption. Perceived utility (PU) is defined by

Hewavitharana, Thathsarani, Nanayakkara, Perera & Perera (2021) as the degree to which a person feels a particular technology will increase their work performance. Surendran (2012) describes perceived ease of use as the extent to which a person perceives that using a specific system would seem to be of no effort (Khan, 2021). According to Jesa (2023), TAM explains technology acceptance as a procedure with three stages in which external variables (system design features) elicit cognitive reactions (perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness), which shape adequate responses (attitudes towards technology use/intentions) which impact how technology is used (Davis, 1989; Davis, 1993). This theory is relevant to this study because it will reveal the likely motivating factors that will enhance social workers use of technology for the practice of their job.

Results and Discussion

Pazer (2024) conducted a quantitative study involving 173 social workers to explore their preparedness for digital tools, perceptions of the impact on work quality, concerns about data security, and workplace support for digitalization. The findings reveal that many social workers feel inadequately prepared to integrate digital technologies into their practice, despite recognizing the potential benefits, such as improved efficiency and expanded service accessibility. However, concerns about data security, ethical considerations, particularly regarding client confidentiality and uneven workplace support pose substantial barriers. In addition, while digital tools can enhance certain aspects of service delivery, they cannot replace the empathy, understanding, and human connection that define the profession. Also, in respect to the future of digital social work practices, social workers are cautiously optimistic about the potential for transformation. Furthermore, while many recognize that digital tools will play an increasingly important role in the profession, there is less consensus about how profound these changes will be. In addition, to them the future of digitalisation will depend on broader systemic factors, such as government policies, funding priorities, and technological advancements. Recommendations were postulated based on the challenges identified as; enhanced training programs, better workplace support, and the development of clear data protection protocols.

This study identified the benefits, challenges, knowledge gap and potentials of digital technologies in social work. This study shows that social workers are not well equipped to navigate the digital world. This is in line with (Granholm, 2019) who commented that social workers often report that they are expected to adopt new tools without sufficient time to learn how to use them effectively. This study therefore suggests a the need for social workers training in digital use and stresses the importance of support to enhance social workers technology adoption. This is supported by Leung & Tsui (2022) who affirmed that those in rural or underfunded areas, may struggle to provide even the most basic digital infrastructure and that without sustained investment in digital infrastructure and professional development, the potential benefits of digitalization may not be fully realized. This situation creates a system where some social workers are skilled in navigating the digital environment while the others are left with ignorance. Hussein (2021) affirmed that another challenge is the digital divide, which refers to disparities in access to digital technologies among different client populations. Banks (2020) also warns that the push towards digitalization must be accompanied by a critical examination of its potential downsides, including the risk of dehumanizing client relationships and reducing social work to a set of technical tasks. Also, Reamer (2021) rightly said social workers are entrusted with sensitive client information, and the increasing use of digital tools raises concerns about data breaches, unauthorized access, and compliance with legal regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Fjeldheim, Kleppe, Stang & Støren-Vaczy (2024) conducted a study using three focus group interviews with educators at three different universities in Norway. They discovered that the knowledge gap is linked to five key findings: uncertainty about the content of the Learning outcomes, unfamiliar technical language, the rapid development of digitalization, the distribution of responsibility and critical reflection. They argued that there must be knowledge about the subject matter (digital competency) that provides a foundation for such critical reflection (digital literacy). According to them, more conceptual clarity is needed regarding the learning outcomes and what digitalization means in an educational context, in order for both digital competency and digital literacy to take their natural place in education. Their research highlights a gap between the competence provided through social work education and the expectations in the practice field. This study shows that educational interventions for social workers doesn't meet their needs. This is in line with Mishna, Bogo, & Sawyer, (2015) who commented that limited education and training prevent many practitioners from knowing how to incorporate technology effectively. Heinsch, Cliff, Tickner, & Betts (2023) supported this finding with the statement that while the use of technology in social work practice has increased, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, there remains a widespread gap in social work education and training on how to use digital technologies effectively and ethically.

Jesa (2023) conducted a qualitative study on how digital technology supplements in-person meetings in social work practice with children and youth. Purposive sampling was used to select children and youth social workers in Lithuania, Latvia, and Slovakia. Data was gathered through online and in-person interviews, then evaluated using content analysis. Document analysis was also used to support this study by assessing each country's DESI (Digital Economy and Society Index) and Ethical Code. Result showed that using digital technologies helps the work to be more effective and supports the intervention process despite the challenges and ethical aspects that must be considered. The intervention process that applies technology helps the client's engagement, encourages the client's change, extends assistance possibility, external support opportunities, and supportive Interdisciplinary Work. Social workers face challenges before applying digital technology and during implementation. They also need to consider some ethical aspects of professional boundaries that might be blurred because of social networks, confidentiality, and informed consent. By using digital technology, social workers not only emphasize its application but also comprehend what it can accomplish, keeping in mind that technology cannot be generalized in all cases and is determined by the client's condition, the available support, and the social worker's ability. Similarly, findings showed that digital technology is beneficial and helps the intervention process if social workers use it properly.

This study addresses the benefits and challenges of digital social work but emphasizes the need for the right use of digital tools to achieve maximum benefits.

Nordesjö & Scaramuzzino (2023) conducted a survey study among 5000 professional social workers that are members of the union for professionals. Findings revealed that most respondents agreed on experiencing increased use of digital tools in the relationship with the clients, increased skills in using digital tools, and a more positive view of digital tools in the social worker–client relationship. However, experiences on whether stress levels had increased and the relationship with the clients worsened, were divided. Age correlates positively with increased stress levels, and social workers working with social assistance, as well as women, are more likely to agree on that the relationship with the clients has worsened. Responses from open-ended questions highlight a

rapid shift where social workers have gained a more positive view of digital tools, that video meetings can increase efficiency and flexibility, but also work environment problems.

This study examines the benefits of digital tools from the perspective of the social workers. It shows that the more the social workers navigate digital platforms, the more likely they are to become skilled in its usage. It also shows the need to develop social workers' competencies in order to reduce the stress associated with technology use for a novice.

Jacob & Souissi (2022) conducted a study titled social workers facing the digital transformation: between potential and threatened professional values. The study was based on a review of international literature and identified the potentials, challenges from user's perspective, as well as the acceptance and appropriation of digital tools. From their review they found out that digital technologies in social work promote the availability and sharing of information, as well as compliance with rules and procedures. Findings revealed that the use of digital tools in social work saves time and increases the effectiveness of interventions, promotes transparency and traceability of interventions, which facilitates the transfer of cases between professionals. In addition, digital technologies provide robust access to all the data and previous interventions, provide and aid sharing of information with staff and other stakeholders, increase intersectoral collaboration and the effectiveness of services to clients. Furthermore, in the case of litigation, it promotes transparency and traceability but also provides protection for stakeholders, it increases the discretion of social workers. Practitioners also affirmed that technology provides greater trust, allows access to more information and is perceived as more reliable than advice from a colleague, contribute to compliant and consistent decision making in a context of frequent regulatory change, can help reduce uncertainty, standardize information that is clearer and easier to analyse. According to them, they opined that studies emphasize that digital technologies save time by using digital tools to automate routine and time-consuming tasks.

Succinctly, Jacob and Souissi (2022) further revealed that achieving this benefit requires not only expertise in the field of social work, but also a good understanding of the technical aspects of the system to evaluate algorithmic decisions and revise them as needed. Therefore, they believe the task of practitioners is no longer focused on problem solving and decision making involving specific professional knowledge but it is now focused on providing a service through technical support.

They identified the following as disadvantages of the use of digital tools; blurring the boundaries between the private and professional spheres which may have repercussions on the work performance and health of workers, accessibility and availability of professionals through these tools often opens the door to new requests for services and increases the number of questions from users, diminished individualised decision of practitioners, issue of stringent procedures imposed by digital system, privacy issues/data protection, algorithmic biases and technology limitations, professional values under threat, limited information about users which may make the social worker lose the link with users, risk of distance leading to the commodification of the user, collecting data in the form of a structured list does not allow for a deep and contextualized understanding of cases. In addition, because of their digital incompetence, some users are at risk of being denied access to social services, the limitations of digital technologies can lead to unreliable decisions, the dematerialization of social work also affects the professional values of social workers. These effects vary widely depending on the technology used and the degree of automation of tasks.

Nevertheless, Jacob and Souissi's study revealed that the reduction of the role of practitioners and their alienation from digital tools can cause frustration and alter their professional fulfillment which may affect job satisfaction as well as the quality of services and the effectiveness of interventions. Also, that social workers use digital technologies in varying ways without necessarily complying with instructions.

They concluded that social workers are often willing to work around the barriers set by digital technologies, so as not to compromise their professional beliefs and appreciate the technology tool when it confirms their views and expectations, they are also willing to reconsider or modify a decision based on the information and suggestions provided by digital tools, their attitude varies according to their general perception of the technology's capabilities and limitations as well as their understanding of the tools' specific operating rules. They also suggested the need for practitioners to listen and react to the individual needs of users.

This study identifies the benefits and challenges of digital transformation of social work. Findings align with previous studies which states that digital tools can increase efficiency, improve access to services, and offer new ways to engage with clients (Granholt, 2019). This is supported by Taylor & McQuaid, (2022) who stated that the use of AI in social work, while still in its infancy, holds promise for improving decision-making processes and resource allocation. Similarly, Digital tools offer new opportunities for enhancing the quality and accessibility of social work services, but they also present challenges such as issues of digital literacy, data security, and equitable access to technology (Chan & Holosko, 2018).

The use of AI and data-driven tools in decision-making processes could potentially undermine the human-centered approach that is central to social work practice (Barsky, 2021). Clients from low-income backgrounds, older adults, and those living in rural areas may lack the necessary infrastructure or digital literacy to fully benefit from digital services (Mishna et al., 2020).

Seun, Lai, Wang, Yin & Lam (2022) conducted an assessment of web-based training platforms specifically i-TLS (innovative web-based training, learning, and sharing) platform developed under the Hong Kong Jockey Club SMART Family-Link Project. The platform demonstrated particular value during COVID-19 restrictions when face-to-face training became impossible. The platform aimed at supporting social workers learning during the early stages of digital transformation. He used 313 users and findings revealed the impact of an innovative learning platform with three different components and learning approaches (I-sharing, I-Training, I-Learning). Evaluation after one year of implementation showed that the platform was acceptable and useful to users. Also, that users were satisfied with the platform and more frequent users showed increased knowledge, knowledge application and self-efficacy than the light users. In addition, Users were positive about the potential use of i-TLS in supporting continuous learning and that it is easily accessible. Some felt uneasy in finding time for learning amid busy professional duties and time pressure. Data suggests that i-TLS could increase support by reaching more social workers across centres at the point of need. ITLS findings reveal that a significant portion of social workers lack the confidence to effectively integrate digital technologies into their practice. Frequent users reported significantly higher gains in knowledge (5.84 vs 4.09), self-efficacy (5.23 vs 3.96), and knowledge application (6.46 vs 1.91) compared to light users.

This study shows that the more social workers use digital tools for learning and service delivery the better they would feel about technology use and suggests the need for continuous training in digital tools through digital platforms to address the issue of busy schedule. This finding aligns with previous research that has identified a skills gap in the profession, particularly when it comes

to digital literacy (Chan & Holosko, 2018). This raises questions about equity and the risk of excluding vulnerable populations from essential services (Granholm, 2019). In the same vein, Mishna et al., (2020) stated that many social workers have not received sufficient training during their formal education, and ongoing professional development opportunities may be limited depending on their organizational context.

Zhu and Andersen (2022) used a multi-methodological approach that included semi-structured interviews with social work educators at a university in Norway to find out the gap between education and practice. They inquired into how local social work education can better facilitate students' digital competence in line with the European Commission's requirements and the reality of front-line practice. The authors found that, although attention to digitalization has increased over the last five years, digital competence still lacks a prominent position in the curricula, and that integrating digital competence or knowledge areas into Norwegian social work education is still limited. They conclude that digital competence needs to be better integrated into social work programmes so that students can meet the requirements of society (Zhu & Andersen, 2022).

This study shows that the curriculum of social workers education hasn't really captured digital literacy. The findings illustrate major problems arising from inequalities in the competencies and use of technologies based on the experience and personality of the social workers which could be remedied by focusing on the process of digital implementation.

Taylor-Beswick (2022) asked students who have completed a social work education programme about how digital development was experienced throughout the course of their professional training. She found extensive digital knowledge and skills gaps among study participants and that digital development still lags across the profession and reliance on algorithms and automated systems may dehumanize client interactions and reduce the scope for individualized, context-sensitive interventions (Taylor & McQuaid, 2022). She concludes that there is need to understand how social work education is preparing students of social work to engage with a digitally saturated world continues to feel urgent (Taylor-Beswick, 2022).

Cook and Zschomler (2020) in their study identified the following as benefits of social work in a digital environment as social workers are more responsive to need, encouraged openness with younger clients, improved relationship with client, better response from client than in face-to-face therapy. According to them social workers face the risk of being static both personally and professionally, digital divide, digital counselling might not be suitable for certain clients. They suggested that the social workers creativity is more important for the successful provision of services using digital tools.

Synthesis of findings

Strengths

Enhanced Efficiency and Service Delivery

Digital technologies contribute significantly to improved efficiency, flexibility, information sharing, and interdisciplinary collaboration within social work practice. Evidence shows that digital tools can strengthen client engagement, improve accessibility to services, and support continuity of care, particularly in constrained contexts such as public health emergencies (Jacob & Souissi, 2022; Jesa, 2023; Nordesjö & Scaramuzzino, 2023).

Support for Complementary, Human-Centered Interventions

When appropriately applied, digital tools function as supplements rather than replacements for face-to-face practice. Studies consistently emphasize that technology can enhance, but not

substitute, empathy, relational engagement, and contextual understanding—core elements of social work professionalism (Pazer, 2024; Jesa, 2023).

Weaknesses

Limited Digital Preparedness and Skills Gaps

A persistent weakness identified across the literature is the inadequate digital preparedness of social workers. Practitioners and educators report insufficient training, unclear learning outcomes, and weak integration of digital competence into social work curricula, resulting in uneven competence levels, anxiety, and ineffective technology use (Pazer, 2024; Fjeldheim et al., 2024; Zhu & Andersen, 2022).

Impact on Professional Identity and Well-being

Digital transformation has uneven effects on social workers' professional identity and well-being. While increased competence fosters positive attitudes toward technology, others—particularly older practitioners—experience heightened stress, role strain, and reduced job satisfaction as professional roles shift toward technical mediation (Nordesjö & Scaramuzzino, 2023).

Opportunities

Education, Training, and Continuous Professional Development

There is strong consensus that sustained digital training through formal education and continuous professional development presents a critical opportunity for strengthening digital practice. Digital learning platforms have demonstrated effectiveness in improving knowledge, self-efficacy, and skill application, provided institutions allocate adequate support and protected learning time (Seun et al., 2022; Heinsch et al., 2023).

Strategic Integration of Digital Competence

Embedding digital literacy and ethical digital practice into social work education and organizational frameworks offers an opportunity to bridge the gap between education and practice, ensuring that practitioners are better equipped to critically assess and apply emerging technologies.

Threats

Ethical Risks and Data Protection Challenges

Ethical concerns including confidentiality breaches, data security risks, privacy violations, and regulatory compliance pose significant threats to the legitimacy and sustainability of digital social work practice. The increasing use of algorithmic systems intensifies concerns regarding biased decision-making, diminished professional autonomy, and dehumanization of services (Pazer, 2024; Reamer, 2021; Banks, 2020).

Digital Divide and Social Inequality

Unequal access to digital infrastructure and skills among practitioners and service users remains a critical threat. Clients in rural, underfunded, or marginalized contexts, as well as social workers operating in resource-poor environments, risk exclusion from digitally mediated services. Without deliberate investment, digitalization may exacerbate existing structural inequalities rather than alleviate them (Leung & Tsui, 2022; Hussein, 2021; Mishna et al., 2020).

Implication of the study

This study highlights that;

1. Social workers must accept and adopt technology if they do not want to be replaced by technology.
2. Social workers must use digital tools constantly to enhance their digital competencies.

3. Social workers need adequate support system to be able to take advantage of online training opportunities and service delivery. There is need to provide support to social workers through developing training programmes and investment in digital resources.
4. The implementation process of digital literacy should be scrutinized, modified or adjusted to suite current trends and must be guided by the principles of marketing. Online training opportunities should be place within arm's reach of the social worker and the beauty of these digital platforms should be shown to the would-be users.
5. Digital marketing/ information literacy should be encouraged. Digital/Information literacy deals with having access to necessary facts required to navigate digital platforms. Digital marketing should be encouraged.
6. Professional development of social workers in digital skills and competencies is essential for continued relevance.

Conclusion

Traditional face-to-face training with a fixed schedule and venue has restricted the reach of social workers in learning. Skill and knowledge exchanges are limited and often confined to colleagues within the same center or organization. The digital transformation of social work training and service delivery in Nigeria represents a significant opportunity to address longstanding challenges in the country's social work system. Given the primary face to face nature of social work practices, keeping social workers in digital environment is challenging. The SWOT analysis reveals that while digitalization offers substantial strengths and opportunities for enhancing social work practice, these benefits are constrained by weaknesses in preparedness and threats related to ethics and inequality. Strategic investment in education, ethical governance, and infrastructural support is essential to ensure that digital transformation aligns with the human-centered values of social work. However, there is pressing need for social workers to expand their reach and engage with service users on digital platforms. If digital tools are efficiently applied to social work training and service delivery, it can increase access and reduce stigma. Limited digital competence may hinder social workers from realizing the potential of ICT to support their practice. With limited exposure to a technology-rich environment, it will be more difficult for social workers to integrate technology into service delivery and training effectively.

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